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STUDIES IN THE CAMPHORQUINONE REARRANGEMENT. PART II.
FORMATION OF 2:3-DIMETHYLCYCLOHEXAN-1-ONE-4-CARBOXYLIC
ACID FROM SANTENONEQUINONE

BY RAM NARAYAN CHAKRAVARTI

Santenonequinone rearranges in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid to give 2:3-dimethylcyclohexan-1-one-4-carboxylic acid. The keto-acid has been degraded to a tricarboxylic acid, $C_8H_{12}O_6$, which has been identified with pentane- $\beta\gamma$ -tricarboxylic acid synthesised by an unambiguous method.

In a previous communication (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 301), the preparation of the racemic modification of 2:2:3-trimethylcyclohexan-4-one-1-carboxylic acid from synthetic camphor by following the method of Samuel and Manasse (*Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 3157; 1902, **35**, 3831) was described. The properties of the above keto-acid (Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*, p. 303) were in excellent agreement with the view held by Simonsen and his co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1295; 1927, 77) regarding the structure of the corresponding dextro-rotatory keto-acid. Whilst experiments are in progress with a view to synthesising the racemic keto-acid of this structure, the properties of which are wholly inconsistent with those of a synthetic acid (Guha and Dasgupta, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, **22A**, XX, 255), it seemed desirable in the meantime to examine the behaviour of other substances, closely related to camphorquinone, towards sulphuric acid. The present communication, however, deals with the product derived from santenonequinone (I).

In the course of their work on teresantallic acid Semmler and co-workers (*Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 446; 1908, **41**, 125) prepared benzylidene santenone (II) which on oxidation with potassium permanganate in acetone solution yielded santenonequinone, m.p. 105° . A few years later, Palmén (*Finska Kemistamsfundet Medd.*, 1927, **36**, 11; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1927, II, 1691) obtained a quinone, m.p. $84-85^\circ$, having presumably the same structure by the action of hydrochloric acid on isonitrososantenone (III) in presence of formaldehyde. It has been suggested (*cf.* Simonsen, *The Terpenes*, Vol. II, p. 220) that the two quinones must be stereoisomeric although no definite proof exists in support of this view.

Palmén's quinone, m.p. $84-85^\circ$, can be prepared more conveniently by the oxidation of santenone with selenium dioxide in presence of acetic anhydride (*cf.* Simonsen, Evans and Ridgion, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 137). The quinone readily forms a beautifully crystalline quinoxaline derivative with *o*-phenylenediamine, m.p. $102-103^\circ$. As stated by Palmén (*loc. cit.*) the quinone forms a colourless hydrate, m.p. $138-40^\circ$, when left exposed to air or on treatment with alkali. The hydrate on heating, however, loses water and gives back the original quinone. A number of careful analyses have shown the quinone hydrate to possess the formula $C_8H_{12}O_2, \frac{1}{2}H_2O$. Obviously, further work will be necessary in order to elucidate the exact nature of the hydrate.

Santenonequinone on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid (*vide experimental*) undergoes rearrangement with remarkable ease leading to the formation of a keto-acid,

$C_9H_{14}O_3$, m.p. 132° , which can be characterised by the formation of a semicarbazone, m.p. 192° . The keto-acid on oxidation with nitric acid gives a crystalline tricarboxylic acid, $C_8H_{12}O_6$, m.p. $181-82^\circ$, with the loss of a carbon atom. The tricarboxylic acid has been definitely shown to be identical with a specimen of pentane- $\beta\gamma\epsilon$ -tricarboxylic acid (V) prepared synthetically as follows:—

Ethyl α -cyano- β -methylsuccinate (Bone and Sprankling, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, **75**, 853) interacts readily with ethyl β -chloropropionate, in presence of sodium ethoxide, forming ethyl γ -cyanopentane- $\beta\gamma\epsilon$ -tricarboxylate (IV).

When digested with sulphuric acid, the cyano-ester (IV) is hydrolysed with the elimination of carbon dioxide and formation of pentane- $\beta\gamma\epsilon$ -tricarboxylic acid, m.p. 182° , identical with the tricarboxylic acid derived from the oxidation of the keto-acid described above. The identity was further established by direct comparison and by the determination of mixed melting point.

It follows therefore that the original keto-acid can have either of the alternative structures (VI) and (VII).

Of these, structure (VI) is to be preferred, since this alone is capable of being brought into satisfactory harmony with the general mechanism suggested, (Ingold *Chem. Soc. Ann. Report*, 1927, p. 122) for the facile rearrangement of camphorquinone in presence of sulphuric acid. Final proof of the structure of the keto-acid, m.p. 132° , however, rests on the synthesis of an acid of structure (VI), which will form the subject matter of a later communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Santenone used in these experiments was supplied by Messrs. Schimmel & Co., and was found to be optically inactive.

dl-Santenonequinone (I).—*dl*-Santenone (2.5 g.) was heated to $140^\circ-150^\circ$ in an oil-bath for 4 hours with acetic anhydride (3 c.c.) and selenium dioxide (3.2 g.). It was then filtered and the black residue of selenium washed with a little hot acetic acid. The solution was diluted with water, carefully neutralised with dilute sodium hydroxide solution, and extracted with ether. The solvent was then evaporated and the residue on distillation gave *dl*-santenonequinone (1.8 g.) as a mixture of solid and liquid. The liquid product was separated by treatment with a little petroleum ether and the residue purified by crystallisation from the same solvent when pure *dl*-santenonequinone was obtained in yellow crystals, m.p. $84-85^\circ$. (Found: C, 70.5; H, 8.0. $C_9H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 71.0; H, 7.9 per cent).

The quinone, on keeping exposed to air, is slowly converted into a colourless crystalline hydrate, practically insoluble in petroleum ether. It crystallises from dilute acetic acid, m.p.

138-40°. This formation of the hydrate takes place readily in presence of dilute aqueous caustic soda. The hydrate loses water on heating and gives back the yellow quinone. (Found: C, 66.7; H, 8.2. $C_9H_{12}O_2$, $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 67.0; H, 8.0 per cent).

The quinone on heating with *o*-phenylenediamine in alcoholic or acetic acid solution gives the *quinoxaline* derivative which crystallises from dilute alcohol in colourless shining crystals, m.p. 102-103°. (Found: C, 79.8; H, 7.3. $C_{13}H_{16}N_2$ requires C, 80.3; H, 7.1 per cent.).

Rearrangement of dl-Santenonequinone in presence of Concentrated Sulphuric Acid: Formation of dl-2:3-Dimethylcyclohexan-1-one-4-carboxylic Acid (VI).—The finely powdered quinone (1 g.) was added gradually with shaking to concentrated sulphuric acid (9 c.c.) cooled in ice. The quinone went into solution with a yellow colour, which gradually disappeared. It was kept in the cold for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and then poured on to powdered ice with stirring. The keto-acid was isolated by extraction with ether after saturating the solution with salt. To free it from neutral impurities, the ethereal solution was extracted with dilute sodium carbonate solution. The aqueous solution was acidified, saturated with salt and extracted with ether. The keto-acid (1 g.) was obtained as a solid which crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether, m.p. 132°. (Found: C, 63.3; H, 8.2. $C_9H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 63.5; H, 8.2 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from spirit, m.p. 192°. (Found: C, 52.5; H, 7.4. $C_{10}H_{17}O_3N_3$ requires C, 52.8; H, 7.4 per cent).

Oxidation of the Keto-acid with Nitric Acid: Formation of Pentane- β - γ -tricarboxylic Acid (V).—The keto-acid (1 g.) was heated carefully on a water-bath with concentrated nitric acid (15 c.c.) diluted with water (10 c.c.). After a few minutes a vigorous reaction started with copious evolution of nitrous gases. The heating was continued for about 1½ hours. The nitric acid was then evaporated off on the water-bath with frequent addition of water. The gummy product, thus obtained, was then triturated with a little concentrated hydrochloric acid and kept for sometime when a crystalline product was obtained. It was drained on a porous plate. The product (0.25 g.) was purified by crystallisation from concentrated hydrochloric acid, m.p. 181-82°. (Found: C, 46.7; H, 5.9. $C_8H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 47.0; H, 5.8 per cent).

Synthesis of Pentane- β - γ -tricarboxylic Acid.

Ethyl γ -Cyanopentane- β - γ -tricarboxylate (IV).—Ethyl α -cyano- β -methylsuccinate (7g.), prepared by condensing ethyl cyanoacetate with ethyl α -bromopropionate in presence of sodium ethylate according to Bone and Sprankling (*loc. cit.*), was added to an ice-cold solution of sodium (0.77 g.) in absolute alcohol (12.5 c.c.). Ethyl β -chloropropionate (5 g.) was then added to it drop by drop with shaking and kept overnight. The reaction was completed by refluxing on the water-bath for 5 hours. The product was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The extract was washed well with water, dried and the ether evaporated. The product remaining distilled at 168°/4 mm., yield 9 g. (Found: C, 57.2; H, 7.2. $C_{16}H_{23}O_6N$ requires C, 57.5; H, 7.3 per cent).

Pentane- β - γ -tricarboxylic Acid (V).—The above product (8.5 g.) was heated on a sand-bath for 40 hours with water (8.5 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (8.5 c.c.). It was then diluted with water, saturated with salt and extracted repeatedly with ether. The solid residue obtained on evaporation of the solvent was crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid, m.p. 182° and found to be identical with the acid obtained by the oxidation of the keto-acid, $C_8H_{14}O_6$, which in its turn was obtained by the rearrangement of santenonequinone (no depression of mixed m.p.). (Found: C, 46.9; H, 5.9; Equiv., 67.85. $C_8H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 47.0; H, 5.8 per cent. Equiv., 68.0.)

The triethyl ester was obtained by esterifying the acid by the alcohol-vapour method, b.p., 145°/4 mm. (Found: C, 57.9; H, 8.5. $C_{14}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 58.3; H, 8.3 per cent).

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STUDIES IN THE CAMPHORQUINONE REARRANGEMENT. PART III. SYNTHESES OF 2:3-DIMETHYLCYCLOHEXAN-1-ONE-4-CARBOXYLIC ACID AND 3:6-DIMETHYLCYCLOHEXAN-1-ONE-4-CARBOXYLIC ACID

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The ketonic acid, $C_9H_{14}O_5$, obtained by the rearrangement of santenonequinone in presence of sulphuric acid has now been definitely identified as 2:3-dimethylcyclohexan-1-one-4-carboxylic acid by direct synthesis of this acid, as well as the isomeric 3:6-dimethylcyclohexan-1-one-4-carboxylic acid by unambiguous methods. Incidentally it has been shown that the Dieckmann condensation of ethyl β -methylpentane- $\alpha\gamma\epsilon$ -tricarboxylate leads to the formation of ethyl 3-methylcyclohexan-1-one-4:6-dicarboxylate and not the isomeric ester ethyl 3-methyl-cyclohexan-1-one-2:4-dicarboxylate.

In a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 319) evidence was brought forward which appeared to show that the keto-acid, $C_9H_{14}O_5$, obtained by the action of sulphuric acid on santenonequinone, could be best represented by the alternative structures (I) and (II). The most satisfactory way of deciding between these two formulæ seemed to be to prepare these acids synthetically and to compare the synthetical acids with the acid obtained from santenonequinone.

Ethyl crotonate has been condensed with ethyl sodio-cyanoacetate (*cf.* Hope and Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 762) and the resulting product on treatment with ethyl β -chloropropionate gives ethyl β -methyl- γ -cyanopentane- $\alpha\gamma\epsilon$ -tricarboxylate (IV, R=H). This on hydrolysis and esterification furnishes the desired ester (III, $R_1=R_2=H$). Ethyl β -methylpentane- $\alpha\gamma\epsilon$ -tricarboxylate on treatment with sodium gives a ketonic ester which can be represented by the alternative structures (V, $R_1=H$; $R_2=CO_2Et$; X=Et) and (V, $R_1=CO_2Et$; $R_2=H$; X=Et).

